

Leimonos Monastery

also known as “Monastery of Saint Ignatios”

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Entry tags: Cenobitic Monastery, Christian, Greece, Graeco-Phrygian, Religious Group, Christian Orthodox, Monastery, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Christian Traditions, Language, Religious Place, Lesbos, Greek

The Monastery of Saint Ignatios, also called Moni Leimonos (meaning “Monastery of the meadow” in Greek) on the Greek island of Lesbos, not far from the small town of Kalloni, was founded in 1526 by Saint Ignatios Agallianos. It was presumably erected on the remains of a Byzantine monastery which was abandoned around 1462, when the island was taken by the Ottomans. There is no evidence, however, regarding its history, apart from references by Saint Ignatios in his Testament (Typikon), who mentions that the Monastery was built on an existing foundation and with his own expenses (“εκ παλαιών θεμελίων” and “εξ ιδίων αναλωμάτων”). Leimonos Monastery, currently known under the name of its founder, was initially dedicated to Archangel Michael. At Leimonos Monastery, Saint Ignatios founded a school known as Leimoniada, where he also taught along with other learned teachers and scholars. Leimoniada school was functioning until 1923. The Monastery, which currently operates as a men’s convent, is avaton (banned on women to enter it) as prescribed by its founder. The katholikon (main church) was founded in 1526. Many renovations have taken place through time, the present structure being the result of 18th-century (1795-1796) works. The timber-roofed three-aisled basilica has a narthex composed of two parts and covered atriums (north and south). It has also five chapels. Four of them (dedicated to Saint John the Theologian, Saint Charalampos, Zoodochos Pigi, and, Saint Alexandros of Mythimna) occupy the corners of the church, while the fifth is located next to the sanctuary. The katholikon is decorated with frescoes from two different periods. The earliest, fragments of which survive in the apse of the sanctuary, date to the late 16th century and follow the style of the Macedonian school that flourished in the 15th century. The latest date to 1800. The inscription in the narthex mentions that they were painted by the Athonite monk Nikiphoros. The church is furnished with a gilded wooden iconostasis in Ottoman baroque style, made by craftspeople from Chios island. The north side of the central group of buildings in the monastery is taken up by the old wing of cells that date from the 16th century. The cell in which Saint Ignatios has lived is on the first floor. In the cell used as a chapel is still preserved a fresco fragment from the 16th century depicting the Presentation of Christ in the Temple. The fragment may have been detached and brought there from the katholikon, probably during the renovation works of the end of the 18th century. The Monastery is surrounded by many chapels. The chapel of the cemetery, outside the walls of the Monastery serves also as an ossuary. It is a 16th-century single-aisle basilica of small dimensions, partly decorated with frescoes (sanctuary) that follow the Cretan style of Byzantine hagiography. It was most probably built during the lifetime of the Monastery’s founder, Saint Ignatios. Another 16th-century chapel is the one dedicated to the Transfiguration of Jesus Christ, which once belonged to the metochion (dependence) of Christ the Saviour that no longer exists, apart from the chapel in question. In the church was preserved a fragment of fresco depicting the Melismos (a symbolic representation of the Holy Eucharist). The Melismos fragment, as well as the important collection of religious objects and artefacts of the Monastery are exhibited at the museum created for showcasing them. Leimonos Monastery owns also an exceptionally rich collection of manuscripts, early printed books and documents, while it houses also a Geological museum and a Folk Art Museum.

Date Range: 1526 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Leimonos Monastery

Region tags: Northern Aegean Islands, Lesbos, Greece

Leimonos Monastery, Lesbos island, Northern Aegean islands, Greece

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spanos, A., and A. Kalamatas, eds. *Ἱερὰ Μονὴ Λειμῶνος. Ἱστορία – Παλαιογραφία – Τέχνη. Πρακτικὰ Συνεδρίου, Μονὴ Λειμῶνος 27-30 Σεπτεμβρίου 2001*. Athens, 2009.
- Source 2: Spanos, A. *Ἱερὰ Πατριαρχικὴ Καὶ Σταυροπηγιακὴ Μονὴ Λειμῶνος*. Athens, 2003.
- Source 3: Pavlopoulos, Nikodimos (Archimandrite). *Το Ἱστορικὸ Τῆς Μονῆς Λειμῶνος Καὶ ὁ Βίος Του Ἀγίου Ἰγνατίου*. Mytilini, 1994.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.monastiria.gr/iera-moni-leimonos-kallonis/>
- Source 1 Description: Description and photos of Leimonos Monastery, Monastries of Greece
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.monastiria.gr/iera-moni-leimonos-kallonis/>
- Source 2 Description: Website of Leimonos Monastery
- Source 3 URL: <https://youtu.be/sfP6wwMmwPI>
- Source 3 Description: Documentary on Leimonos Monastery by the National Greek Television

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: Meadows and orchards

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery is located 3 km from the town of Kalloni

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is located 3 km from the town of Kalloni

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Both communal and individual worship

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The Monastery founded by Saint Ignatios was not destroyed. However, he founded the present Monastery on the remains of a Byzantine monastery which was abandoned around 1462, when the island was taken by the Ottomans

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

- Renaissance
- Post-Renaissance

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In modernity
– Renaissance
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: The Monastery was initially dedicated to Archangel Michael

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: It was later dedicated to Saint Ignatios, the founder of the Monastery

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: Monks and in particular the male members (his father and son) of the family of Saint Ignatios Agallianos, who became monks along with him, after the death of the female members of their family

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery was built within the land that belonged to its founder, Saint Ignatios Agallianos.

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Saint Ignatios founded the Monastery for becoming himself and his male family members monks

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Meadows and orchards

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon (main church) of the Monastery is the centre of the spiritual and everyday life of the monks and the pilgrims/visitors

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments and binders used for the frescoes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments and binders

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon is decorated with frescoes from two different periods. The earliest, fragments of which survive in the apse of the sanctuary, date to the late 16th century and follow the style of the Macedonian school that flourished in the 15th century. The latest date to 1800. The inscription in the narthex mentions that they were painted by the Athonite monk Nikiphoros. The cell in which Saint Ignatios has lived is

still preserved a fresco fragment from the 16th century. The fragment may have originated from the katholikon, and it may have been moved during the renovation of the end of the 18th century. The Monastery is surrounded by many chapels. The chapel of the cemetery, outside the walls of the Monastery serves also as an ossuary. It is a 16th-century single-aisle basilica of small dimensions, partly decorated with frescoes (sanctuary) that follow the Cretan style of Byzantine hagiography. It was most probably built during the lifetime of the Monastery's founder, Saint Ignatios. In the 16th-century chapel dedicated to the Transfiguration of Jesus Christ is preserved a fragment of fresco depicting the Melismos (a symbolic representation of the Holy Eucharist). The fragment in question, as well as the important collection of religious objects and artefacts of the Monastery are exhibited at the museum of Leimonos.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Icons, iconostasis

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, the Son of God is depicted

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, Seraphim and Cherubim

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Virgin Mary

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: They are included in the scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Notes: The church is furnished with a gilded wooden iconostasis in Ottoman baroque style, made by craftspeople from Chios island.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons on the iconostasis and on the walls of the various buildings of the Monastery

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The Monastery owns illuminated manuscripts as well

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Notes: Inscriptions in Christian Orthodox monuments always have an informative role

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions in Christian Orthodox monuments always have an informative role

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The latest frescoes of the katholikon date to 1800. The inscription in the narthex mentions that they were painted by the Athonite monk Nikiphoros

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Brickwork on the exterior walls

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim and seraphim

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Lives of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Lives of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Mainly portraits of Saints, Evangelists, Prophets, Jesus Christ, Angels and Virgin Mary

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: The monks and pilgrims/visitors pray and worship God at the Monastery

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: The monks of the Monastery and the visitors/pilgrims pray and worship God at this place

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims and visitors come to pray and worship God at the Monastery

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: At least a service (Divine Liturgy) every Sunday and services and other Mysteries whenever it is possible or necessary

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Impossible to specify

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: At least a service (Divine Liturgy) every Sunday and services and other Mysteries whenever it is possible or necessary

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian Orthodox rite is followed

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian Orthodox rite is followed

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to Orthodox monasteries can vary from food to very valuable objects or even land

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to Orthodox monasteries can vary from food to very valuable objects or even land

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Offerings to Orthodox monasteries can vary from food to very valuable objects or even land. Leimonos Monastery was built within the land owned by Agallianos family, of which Saint Ignatios was a member

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance is required for the conservation of the buildings of the Monastery dating to the 16th century

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery underwent significant renovations, as well as minor repairs for its conservation and preservation

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The Hellenic Ephorate of Antiquities of Lesbos and the Metropolis of Mithimna are in charge

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Since this is a listed monument, many specialists study and are charged with the preservation and conservation of the buildings and the movable artefacts of Leimonos Monastery

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Following the Orthodox liturgical calendar

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The monks of the Monastery always participate and male pilgrims whenever they wish. Women are not allowed to enter the katholikon (main church) of the Monastery

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Impossible to specify

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: This is a male monastic community

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot (higoumenos) is the leader of the monastic community

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The Monastery included a schools, Leimonias, founded by Saint Ignatios

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Metropolis of Mithimna and the Hellenic Ephorate of Antiquities of Lesbos

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Leimonos Monastery owns an exceptionally rich collection of manuscripts, early printed books and documents

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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